

Time-resolved Dissociative Ionization and Double-Photoionization of CO₂

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Abstract:

CO₂ single-photon double-photoionization, Coulomb explosion and dissociative ionization are studied with ultrafast extreme-ultraviolet pump and time-delayed near-IR probe pulses. Kinetic energy release and momentum correlations for the two-body CO⁺ + O⁺ and three-body O⁺ + C⁺ + O fragmentation products are determined by 3D coincidence fragment imaging. Transient enhancement of the ratio of two-body versus three-body Coulomb explosion events, as well as the time dependence of low and high kinetic energy release dissociation events are discussed in terms of dissociative ionization and Coulomb explosion dynamics.

Introduction:

Ionization of carbon dioxide has been extensively studied due to its importance to different planetary and plasma environments.¹⁻⁴ For ionization energies above a ~37 eV threshold, double-ionization can form a metastable CO₂²⁺ dication.⁵ Although it lies over 4 eV above its CO⁺ + O⁺ dissociation limit, potential barriers of more than 1 eV, efficiently prevent the decay

of its ground state.^{6,7} The metastable CO_2^{2+} dication was first observed by Conrad in early “canal-ray” studies.⁸ Its formation as well as dissociation were studied by electron-impact ionization,^{9–14} by collisions with fast ion beams,^{15–18} by intense laser multi-photon ionization^{19–24} and by single photon double-photoionization.^{5,25–32} The double-photoionization cross-section of carbon dioxide rises with the photon energy and reaches ~33% of the single ionization yield at ~100 eV.²⁶ The metastable CO_2^{2+} was predicted to exist in the atmospheres of different planetary systems such as Venus³³ and Mars.³⁴ While CO_2^{2+} production in the upper Martian atmosphere is dominated by photoionization of CO_2^+ , below 190 km altitudes CO_2^{2+} is formed by double photionization.³⁵ Mars missions to investigate its CO_2 dominated atmosphere confirmed the predicted presence of a CO_2^{2+} dication.³⁶ The stability and lifetime of the CO_2^{2+} dication were studied by different methods that explored different time scales. Long, practically stable ~4 s storage lifetimes were observed for the CO_2^{2+} ground state in heavy ion storage ring experiments, limited by the dications collision with the residual gas molecules in the ultra-high vacuum apparatus.^{37,38} Shorter lifetimes were determined for hot dications formed by photoionization, or by electron impact ionization, ranging from the nanosecond to the microsecond time scales.^{5,27,39–42} Ultrafast pump-probe studies of carbon dioxide, using multi-photon ionization with intense femtosecond laser pulses were shown to exhibit ultrafast dication yield modulations that were attributed to dynamics on intermediate singly ionized CO_2^+ states.⁴³ Under different intense laser parameters, Rudenko *et. al.* observed additional modulations as a function of pump-probe delay that were assigned to vibrational and rotational dynamics of both the neutral and cation ground states.⁴⁴

Multi-photon ionization and dissociation in intense laser fields are most sensitive to the exact pulse length, peak intensity and chirp of the intense laser pulse.^{45–47} It is therefore attractive to perform time-resolved photoionization studies using ultrafast extreme ultraviolet (EUV) pulses that are made possible using high-order harmonic generation (HHG),^{48–50} synchrotron based pulse slicing methods,⁵¹ as well as ultrafast free electron lasers.^{52,53} With the advent of

high photon energies, photoionization and even double-photoionization proceed without the presence of an intense laser field, making the theoretical modeling with state of the art quantum chemistry simulations feasible.⁵⁴⁻⁵⁶ The CO₂ system is most interesting for such EUV pump-probe studies, not only due to its relative simplicity, but also as it exhibits a particularly high single-photon double-photoionization fraction compared to the total ion yield. Here, we report a study of CO₂ photoionization using an ultrafast EUV pump pulse, followed by a time resolved near-infrared (NIR) probe pulse. Stable CO₂⁺, CO₂²⁺, dissociative ionization (DI) and Coulomb explosion (CE) products are detected by 3D coincidence fragment imaging. The competing DI and CE processes are discussed in view of their kinetic energy release (KER) and time-resolved pump-probe signals.

Experimental:

The single-photon CE imaging spectrometer used in this study has been described in detail before.⁵⁴⁻⁵⁷ In brief, sub 35fs NIR pulses, centered around 800 nm, are generated at a 1 kHz repetition rate.⁵⁸ The ~6 mJ laser output is split: ~2 mJ are focused in a semi-infinite neon gas cell to produce broadband EUV pulses by HHG.⁵⁹ The EUV pulses are spatially filtered⁶⁰ from the higher divergence NIR and are directed to cross an effusive CO₂ molecular beam at the center of a 3D coincidence fragment imaging spectrometer.⁵⁴ The remaining ~4 mJ NIR pulses are time-delayed and mildly focused to overlap with the EUV beam at a small ~1° angle. Cationic products are accelerated by spectrometer potentials and detected on a position and time sensitive MCP detector, equipped with P46 phosphor anode. The fragments charge/mass ratios are determined by their time-of-flight (TOF) with the timing signal being digitized by a fast scope, while 2D positions are read out using a CCD camera.⁶¹ Coincident times and positions are correlated by the respective amplitudes of the scope and CCD signals.^{61,62} Thus, the time and position information allows to record the 3D momenta of single or multiple cations produced from each laser shot.⁶³

Results and discussion:

In contrast to the previously studied systems using our setup, in which double-ionization resulted in CE,⁵⁴⁻⁵⁷ doubly ionized CO₂ supports a metastable undissociated CO₂²⁺ dication.⁵ With a 44/2 mass over charge ratio, the TOF of metastable dications to the detector is identical to that of the ²²Ne⁺ isotope, which is present in the HHG source. Nevertheless, 3D imaging allows disentangling the contribution of the metastable species from the low abundance isotope. Figure 1 shows 2D position distributions, measured in the detector plane for different ion TOF's that correspond to mass over charge ratios of 44 (CO₂⁺), 20 (²⁰Ne⁺) and 22 (both ²²Ne⁺ and CO₂²⁺). The stable CO₂⁺ ion peak in figure 1a is shifted in the Y direction from the optical center of the spectrometer due to the momentum of the parent CO₂ molecules of the molecular beam. The narrow position distribution spread of the undissociated parent ion reflects the narrow velocity distribution of the skimmed molecular beam. CO₂⁺ cations originating from the room temperature residual background pressure of CO₂ contribute to the broader isotropic distribution around the center of the spectrometer. In contrast, ²⁰Ne⁺ cation distribution shown in figure 1b exhibits a shift in the X direction, as neon atoms reach the spectrometer from the HHG source through a series of apertures, moving along the EUV beam path in the X axis direction. As opposed to the CO₂ effusive beam, which is directed into a 700 L/S turbo molecular pump, the Neon gas collides with the vacuum chamber walls before being pumped – resulting in a slightly higher contribution from neon residual gas. Both the molecular beam and neon features are observed in the m/q=22 signal shown in figure 1c, which is attributed to both CO₂²⁺ dications and rare ²²Ne⁺ isotope ions. The neon isotope background can be estimated and subtracted based on the ²⁰Ne⁺ signal, for convenience the m/q=20 distribution shown in figure 1b is multiplied by the 9.25 / 90.48 ratio of the two stable neon isotopes,⁶⁴ clearly accounting for the ²²Ne⁺ ion contribution to the measured signal with mass/charge ratio of 22 shown in figure 1c. The yield of undissociated metastable CO₂²⁺ is obtained by selecting m/q=22 ions with no recoil with respect to the molecular beam and

subtracting the estimated $^{22}\text{Ne}^+$ background based on the $m/q=20$ signal. It is important to note that the ion trajectories in the electrostatic potential scale with $1/\sqrt{q}$ such that the positions of doubly charged CO_2^{2+} ions originating from the molecular beam are scaled by $1/\sqrt{2}$ compared to the CO_2^+ ions, as indicated by the ellipse labeled " CO_2^{2+} " in figure 1c.

Figure 1. 2D fragment imaging data: a) showing ions with mass to charge ratio ($m/q = 44$), assigned to CO_2^+ . b) $m/q = 20$ ions assigned to $^{20}\text{Ne}^+$. c) $m/q = 22$ ions originating both from $^{22}\text{Ne}^+$ as well as CO_2^{2+} . For comparison with panel c, panel b count rates are scaled by the natural abundance ratio of the stable ^{22}Ne and ^{20}Ne isotopes. Similarly, the singly ionized CO_2^+ signal in panel (a) is scaled down by a factor of 20. MB, RG and Ne indicate the contributions assigned to undissociated ions originating in the molecular beam, residual gas and neon from the HHG region respectively.

Coulomb explosion of the doubly-ionized system results in a two cation coincidence signal. These events can be disentangled from random coincidences of DI of two separate CO_2 molecules by total momentum conservation. Any residual random coincidence contributions can be effectively subtracted based on the measured probabilities of the individual ion signals. Figure 2a shows the total momentum distribution of coincident $\text{CO}^+ + \text{O}^+$ events in the XY detector plane. Similar to the intact CO_2^+ , shown in fig 1a, the center of mass (CM) momentum is shifted in the Y axis direction, reflecting the momentum of the parent CO_2 molecules from the molecular beam. For comparison, fig 2b shows the expected CM momentum distribution of random coincidence background, estimated based on the measured rates of individual CO^+ and O^+ events. The higher spread of random coincidence events allows its effective suppression by selecting events with no recoil with respect to the molecular beam. Furthermore, the low count rate results in a particularly low random coincidence rate - note

that the estimated random coincidence signal is multiplied by a x600 factor to be presented on the same intensity scale as the true coincidence CE events. Figure 2c shows the CM momentum of coincident $C^+ + O^+$ ions. As the measured data shows no significant triple ionization contributions, these events are assigned as $C^+ + O^+ + O$ three-body dissociation events. The measured spread of the CM momentum reflects therefore the recoil of the undetected neutral oxygen atom. The CM spread limits the rejection of random coincidence events. Nevertheless, random coincidence contribution can be estimated and subtracted based on the individual rates of C^+ and O^+ ions. Figure 2d shows the estimated CM momentum spread of the random C^+ and O^+ coincidences. For the $O^+ + O^+ + C$ channel, only minor contributions were observed.

Figure 2 . Center of mass momentum of a) $CO^+ + O^+$ channel. b) Simulated CM spread of random coincidences of CO^+ and O^+ ions. c) $C^+ + O^+$ coincidences, assigned to the $C^+ + O^+ + O$ channel. d) Simulated CM spread of random coincidences of C^+ and O^+ ions.

The respective yields of double-ionization channels $CO_2^{2+} / CO^+ + O^+ / C^+ + O^+ + O$ were found to be 6 / 24 / 8 for every 100 intact singly ionized CO_2^+ parent cations, in agreement with literature for photoionization in the 50-70 eV photon energy range.²⁶ Laksman *et. al.* report also $C^+ + O_2^+$ CE following core-level excitation ($1s \rightarrow \pi^*$) of the carbon and oxygen atoms, respectively with 290 and 535 eV photon energies produced in a soft x-ray undulator.³⁰ This

unusual rearrangement of the linear O-C-O structure was attributed to a Renner-Teller effect for the core-excited states. Furthermore, based on analysis of dication fragmentation within their TOF spectrometer, Alagia *et. al.* as well as Slattery *et. al.* report metastable CO_2^{2+} near the 37.3 eV threshold, with lifetime as short as 50 ns.^{5,27} However, our measurements show no significant yields of $\text{C}^+ + \text{O}_2^+$ CE, nor of metastable CO_2^{2+} decays on the 100 ns - few μs time scale within the experimental error. This is consistent with the high above threshold photon energies, up to ~ 100 eV, produced from HHG in the neon gas cell.^{54,65}

The $\text{C}^+ + \text{O}^+$ CM recoil in the XY plane, which distribution is shown in figure 2c, allows calculation of the momentum carried away by the undetected neutral oxygen fragment for each dissociation event and reveals the three-body momentum correlations. The measured three-body momentum correlations are represented using Dalitz plot coordinates derived using the kinetic energies of the three fragments.^{66,67} The low background contribution of random coincidence C^+ and O^+ events is estimated and subtracted based on the individual ion rates. Figure 3a shows the weighted, mass-scaled Dalitz plot of the three-body momentum correlation for the $\text{C}^+ + \text{O}^+ + \text{O}$ channel.^{56,68,69} As opposed to the original Dalitz plot mapping that was developed for fragments of equal mass,^{66,67} the generalized Dalitz plot, developed by Luzon *et. al.*,⁵⁶ uses the respective KER fraction carried by each fragment, E/KER , scaled by the maximal energy fraction that can be carried by the fragments mass. Thus, for the three-body dissociation of CO_2 , the mass scaled KER fractions are defined as $\epsilon_{\text{C}^+} \equiv \frac{E_{\text{C}^+}}{\text{KER}} \times \frac{44}{32}$ and $\epsilon_{\text{O}/\text{O}^+} \equiv \frac{E_{\text{O}/\text{O}^+}}{\text{KER}} \times \frac{44}{28}$. Each position on the Dalitz plot corresponds to a particular energy partitioning between the three fragments. For convenience, the mass-scaled energy axes ϵ_{O} , ϵ_{O^+} and ϵ_{C^+} are indicated on the figure 3a. Furthermore, figure 3b shows the 3-body momentum correlations, corresponding to different positions on the generalized Dalitz plot. Same as for the original Dalitz plot, a random uncorrelated dissociation appears as a uniform distribution within the unit circle defined by energy and momentum conservation. Taking into

consideration the better absolute momentum resolution in the XY position measurements as well as the nearly isotropic product distribution, following references 68 and 56, the measured correlations in the 2D plane of the detector are weighted by a simulated distribution of uncorrelated three-body breakup events. Thus, an uncorrelated dissociation would result in a uniform distribution within the unit circle. The measured Dalitz plot in figure 3a exhibits a higher probability near the edge of the unit circle, indicating co-linear dissociation patterns that reflect the initial $D_{\infty h}$ geometry of the parent CO_2 molecule, with the central carbon cation positioned along the line between the two oxygen atoms. As the symmetry between the neutral O and O^+ cation is broken, the O^+ cation is ejected with a higher kinetic energy – resulting in recoil of the central C^+ cation towards the neutral O atom. Similar asymmetric breakups were previously reported in electron impact ionization,¹⁰ and photoionization with 60 eV photons.³⁰ In these studies the symmetric recoil of the neutral and cationic oxygen were assigned to concerted 3-body dissociation, while the asymmetric recoil was attributed to a sequential breakup in which $CO^+ + O^+$ CE precedes dissociation of the molecular fragment. It is important to note that in sequential breakup, rotations of the CO^+ intermediate are expected to result in equal probability of the C^+ and neutral O fragments to be ejected in the direction of the O^+ cation. The generalized Dalitz coordinates allow to clearly visualize that in contrast, the momentum correlation measured here indicate the clear preference of the C^+ to remain between the two oxygen atoms. As shown in figure 2b map of three-body momentum triangles to the generalized Dalitz plot coordinates, co-linear $O^+—C^+—O$ fragmentation contributes to the upper right-hand side of the Dalitz plot, while the analogous $O^+—O—C^+$ would contribute to the upper left-hand side. Thus, we do not attribute the three-body $O + C^+ + O^+$ breakup observed here to a sequential mechanism, rather to a complex concerted CE mechanism. Furthermore, the high KER fraction carried away by the neutral oxygen atom suggests it is ejected during the CE process. In the three-body breakup of doubly-ionized methanol, Luzon *et. al.*⁵⁶ showed that a surprisingly high fraction of the total

KER can be carried away by neutral products of CE. Where ab initio molecular dynamics simulations of the methanol dication suggested that the high recoil of neutral fragments arises from transient charge oscillations within the CE complex.⁵⁶ It is interesting to note that despite of the linear geometry of CO₂, bending vibration result in a most probable 174.6° O-C-O angle for the neutral ground state.⁷⁰ Thus, the three-body momentum correlations are not expected to be strictly co-linear in agreement with the finite deviation of the measured data from the rim of the unit circle in figure 3a.

Figure 3. C⁺ + O⁺ + O three body breakup momentum correlations. a) Weighted Dalitz plot of the measured correlations. Where the $\epsilon_{O/O^+/C^+}$ axis indicate the mass scaled kinetic energy fractions of each fragment b) Mapping of different areas on the Dalitz plot to the corresponding three-body dissociation geometries. Red and grey circles are oxygen and carbon atoms respectively and plus signs denote the cation fragments.

The 3D coincidence imaging of all the correlated CE products allows analysis of the fragmentation in the CM frame of the dissociating complex. Figure 4 shows the measured CO⁺ + O⁺ KER spectrum. The measured KER distribution peaks at ~5.5 eV, in agreement with previous double-photoionization studies above 44 eV.³² Based on ab initio CASPT2 potential energy calculations as a function of one of the C-O distances, while constraining the other degrees of freedom, Zhang *et. al.* predicted KER in the 5-13 eV range depending on the excited state of the dication and dissociation products excitation.⁷ Unrestricted non-adiabatic molecular dynamics initialized on excited states of a methanol dication were shown to exhibit ultrafast C-O bond breaking.⁵⁶ Although individual methanol dication states showed barriers towards C-O dissociation, the simulated unrestricted dynamics that are facilitated by multiple surface hopping events resembled dissociation on a diabatic Coulombic repulsion potential.⁵⁴

Following Luzon *et. al.*,⁵⁴ we can estimate the expected KER considering a simple $\frac{1}{4\pi\epsilon R_{12}}$ Coulombic potential. Where the effective permittivity ϵ is taken to be $1.25\epsilon_0$ according to the phenomenological double-photoionization threshold law developed by Eland and co-workers.⁷¹ R_{12} is the effective distance between the holes created by removing a pair of electrons from the parent molecule. Based on the CO_2 linear geometry and its $R_{\text{CO}}=1.163 \text{ \AA}$ distance, two limiting cases can be considered: The vertical black arrow indicating 9.9 eV KER on figure 4 corresponds to the short distance (and high KER) limit, assuming ionization of the carbon and one of the neighboring oxygen atoms at the R_{12} distance of R_{CO} . The arrow indicating KER of 5.45eV, corresponds to the $R_{12}=2R_{\text{CO}}$, the maximal distance (and low KER) within the CO_2 molecule – in agreement with the measured KER range. The measured KER peak is at $\sim 5.5 \text{ eV}$, near the low KER limit. It corresponds to an effective inter-charge distance $R_{12} \sim 1.8 R_{\text{CO}}$ and ionization of the two oxygen atoms. This result supports dissociation on the excited states of the dication, as half of the positive charge of the dication ground state was predicted to be on the central carbon atom.⁶

Figure 4. KER spectrum of the $\text{CO}^+ + \text{O}^+$ CE channel. Black arrows indicate the expected KER limits based on a simple Coulombic repulsion model. Inset shows the angularly resolved dissociation velocity distribution with respect to the laser electric field polarization axis.

Figure 4 inset shows the angularly-resolved momentum distribution of the $\text{CO}^+ + \text{O}^+$ events with respect to the vertical laser polarization. The angular distribution of the main KER peak

is rather isotropic and is fitted with a $\beta = -0.16$ anisotropy parameter. This in agreement with previous double-photoionization studies using narrow bandwidth synchrotron radiation that showed photon energy dependent anisotropy in the 60-100 eV that reduces to an isotropic $\beta = 0$ with increasing photon energy.⁷²

With the advent of ultrafast EUV bursts produced by HHG, it is possible to probe the ultrafast breakup dynamics initiated by the EUV pulse with a time-delayed NIR pulse. Figure 5a shows the time resolved ratio of 2-body to 3-body CE yields. As opposed to our previous EUV pump – NIR probe studies in the N₂O and CH₃OH systems, for which NIR excitation of the transient complex promoted fragmentation of multiple bonds and three-body dissociation, here the two-body breakup fraction is transiently enhanced. In our previous EUV pump NIR probe studies of N₂O and of CH₃OH,^{55,57} the time delayed NIR probe pulse was found to promote lower lying states of the dication, which main products are two-body breakup channels, to higher lying states that facilitate also 3-body fragmentation. In contrast, excitation of the practically stable CO₂²⁺ ground state can enhance two-body CE and account for the observed feature. However, the transient nature of the two-body CE enhancement suggests a relaxation mechanism that quenches CE at long $t_{\text{NIR}} > 300$ fs time delays. It is therefore also possible that the transient enhancement reflects a 2nd ionization by the NIR probe of high lying singly ionized CO₂⁺ transients that decay at long time delays, e.g. by DI. Furthermore, at long NIR time delays, the ratio falls below its initial levels, suggesting also photodissociation of the molecular 2-body CE product by the NIR pulse.

Figure 5. Time resolved product yields: a) Ratio of the main two-body and three-body CE channels as a function of the NIR time delay. b) Red circles show time resolved yield of high kinetic energy CO^+ ions, assigned to CE. Blue cross symbols indicate the time resolved yield of low KER CO^+ yield, assigned to ionization of CO^* DI products.

While CO_2^+ is the dominant photoionization product (70%), significant $\text{O}^+ + \text{CO}$ (~16%) DI yield is observed along with lower yields corresponding to C^+ and CO^+ , in agreement with previously published measurements.²⁶ The relatively low CO^+ contribution from DI, along with relatively high CE rates, make it possible to observe high KER CO^+ , originating from the main single-photon CE channel, even if the coincident O^+ is not detected due to the finite detection efficiency. Figure 6 shows the KER distribution, calculated from the measured CO^+ recoil in the plane of the detector. The smooth red lines in figure 6 help distinguish the contributions of low KER dissociative ionization events and high KER CE events, fitted with one and two Gaussian functions respectively. The high KER CO^+ signal, attributed to CE, and the low KER DI signals exhibit very different dependencies on the NIR time delay. As shown in figure 5b, high KER CE event yield exhibits a broad transient peak, fitted with a ~300 fs FWHM Gaussian, centered at the time overlap of the EUV pump and NIR probe pulses; Similar to the transient enhancement feature in the 2-body/3-body branching ratio shown in figure 5a. In contrast,

the low KER CO^+ signal, characteristic of DI, rises during the time of the high kinetic energy transient, reaching a $\sim 15\%$ increase plateau that persists at long time delays.

Figure 6. KER of CO^+ single coincidence, derived under the assumption of two-body dissociation. Red curves help visualize the high and low KER contributions.

We therefore conclude that the observed pump-probe signals reflect the time-resolved DI dynamics on high lying CO_2^{+*} states: NIR photoionization of the transient CO_2^{+*} contributes to the high KER $\text{O}^+ + \text{CO}^+$ signal, accounting for the transient enhancement of the 2-body/3-body ratio as well as the correlated increase in high KER CO^+ yield. The excited CO_2^{+*} transient decays by DI within the $\sim 300\text{fs}$ time of its excitation by the EUV pump pulse, dissociating into low KER $\text{O}^+ + \text{CO}^*$. The excited CO^* DI products can then be efficiently ionized by the NIR pulse at long time delays and produce the observed rise and plateau observed for the low KER CO^+ ion yield.

Conclusions:

Time resolved imaging of DI and CE products of an ultrafast EUV-pump and a time delayed NIR-probe pulse were performed. The $\sim 5.5\text{ eV}$ KER in the $\text{CO}^+ + \text{O}^+$ 2-body CE agrees with rapid dissociation of the CO bond following double-photoionization of the two oxygen atoms with an effective $1.8 R_{\text{CO}}$ inter-charge distance. Three-body momentum correlations also indicate a rapid dissociation, conserving the co-linear geometry with a C^+ positioned between the O^+ and

the O fragments. The observed time resolved dynamics are attributed to ionization of a transient CO_2^{+*} created by the EUV pulse, enhancing the main CE channel $\text{CO}^+ + \text{O}^+$. The CO_2^{+*} transient decays by DI on the 300 fs time scale, such that at long time delays the probe ionizes low KER neutral DI products of the transient cation. As the dominant DI channel appears to be $\text{O}^+ + \text{CO}^*$, ionization of the CO^* contributes to the observed $\sim 15\%$ increase in the low kinetic energy CO^+ ions at long time delays. Further experimental and theoretical work is needed to explore the dication dynamics. The relatively efficient population of the metastable CO_2^+ dication with ultrafast EUV pulses makes it a particularly suitable system to study exotic dication dynamics on ultrafast time scales. Its relative simplicity can allow detailed comparison with theoretical modeling of the dication dynamics as well as the single-photon double-ionization itself. Furthermore, with the advent of free electron laser facilities,⁷³ which can provide ultrafast pulses at even higher photon energies, it will also be possible to time resolve the reported³⁰ structural rearrangement dynamics responsible for O_2^+ products.

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